
Review

IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING ON BRAND LOYALTY IN FASHION INDUSTRY: EVIDENCE FROM UK

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Abstract: This research examines the role of “social media marketing (SMM)” in influencing brand loyalty (BL) in the context of UK fashion firms. Employing secondary qualitative data, the study explores the deployment of SM, consumer interactions and effective strategies that affect consumer purchasing behaviour and BL. Primary insights highlight that extended influencer marketing and active engagements are productive in strengthening consumer loyalty. Significantly, consistent appreciation from influencers makes the product more likely to be bought while a high level of engagement enhances the bond between the consumers. Suggestions consist of focusing on constant and large-scale collaborations with influencers, increasing the level of interactivity of the content, targeting individual consumers, and increasing the level of trust. It emphasises on the importance of employing targeted strategies on social media (SM) sites for improving customer loyalty and is a good source of information for fashion-based organizations seeking to enhance the loyalty level of their customers. The limitations of the study are the use of secondary data and the sample is restricted to the UK only, it is recommended that future research should focus on newly developing platforms, differences across the regions, and the primary data for more general findings.

Keywords: Social media marketing; Brand loyalty; Fashion industry; UK

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Introduction

In the past few years, digital marketing has drastically influenced the fashion industry moving a shift from conventional advertisement to more content marketing. As stated by Yeo et al. (2022), “social media marketing (SMM)” has made it easy for brands or companies to access consumers and other stakeholders with ease, interact with them in real-time, come up with customized content and expand their client base. Visuals, endorsements from influencers, and use of interactive content which are some of the key attributes of social media (SM) media are instrumental in influencing consumer decisions when making a purchase. In a survey that was conducted in February 2022 in the United Kingdom over one-third of fashion and lifestyle buyers said that they use Instagram as their inspiration to shop for fashion/lifestyle products including “apparel, fashion accessories, health and beauty, and the home interiors” (Stacy Jo Dixon, 2023). On the other hand, the frequency of Facebook usage was below 20%, with TikTok and YouTube users comprising approximately 13% of the sample.

Figure 1.1: “Social media sources of inspiration used by fashion & lifestyle buyers in UK”

(Source: Stacy Jo Dixon, 2023)

1.2 Problem Statement

While the extant literature emphasizes the significance of SMM in the fashion industry, there is limited research on metrics determining the impact of such strategies on brand loyalty (BL), especially within the UK context. As major platforms like Instagram and TikTok start shaping consumers' behaviour more and more, the role of these strategies in creating BL is unclear (Rienda, Ruiz-Fernandez & Carey, 2021). Marketers spend significant amounts on SM promotion, and, thus, tracking the effectiveness of these promotions on consumer retention requires a combination of criteria including content, level of interaction, and platform. This research will aim to fill this gap by assessing the impact of SMM strategies on BL amongst fashion consumers in UK.

1.3 Aim, Objectives and Question

Research Aim

The aim of this research is to examine the impact of SMM on BL within the fashion industry in the UK

Objectives

- To analyse the impact of SMM strategies on BL in UK
- To assess the role of consumer engagement on SM in enhancing loyalty in UK
- To recommend effective SM practices for improving BL in fashion

Research question

- How does SMM influence BL in the UK fashion industry?

1.4 Significance of the Study

Fashion brands need to have a proper understanding of SM specifically because it influences buyer behaviour, their mode of interaction with a chosen brand, as well as their level of BL (Fetais et al. 2023). These findings can be very useful for fashion brands, as they go as far as discovering how to utilise SM platforms that affect BL among customers. The research outcomes can be used by marketers to create appropriate SM strategies which create customer attraction and maintain customer satisfaction through improving engagement and community feelings.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Brand Loyalty

BL is the extent to which a consumer pledges to purchase or repeatedly use the products or services of a particular brand. As stated by Fetais et al. (2023), this includes the brand's ability to command multiple repurchases by the customers, or what can also be referred to as behavioural loyalty as well as the affections of the customers which can also be referred to as attitudinal loyalty. BL is significant in the fashion industry since it keeps the consumers coming back for more and increases patronage. Djafarova & Bowes (2021) claim that BL stems from the quality of products, brand equity relations with the brand and special experiences.

2.2 Impact of SMM on Brand Loyalty

In the process of brand management, SMM has a very important role in influencing the perception and engagement of consumers. This is supported by Jacobson & Harrison (2022) who opine that SM campaigns help improve BL through 'personalised content & direct engagement' thereby promoting the cultivation of 'emotional ties. In contrast, Djafarova & Bowes (2021) posit that SM affects consumer loyalty depending on the coherence of brand communication and the proper selection of influential partners promoting enhanced customer trust and loyalty. The two are consistent with the enhanced focus on both, the individual relationships as well as the macro-strategic approach to make the best out of the SM channel to foster BL.

2.3 Role of consumer engagement on SM in enhancing loyalty

SM consumer engagement is therefore critical for increasing BL due to the promotion of interaction and community. Khoa (2020) emphasizes that simple interactions, including commenting and replying, help create trust and establish the kind of bonds that lead to loyalty. On the other hand, Park, Im & Kim (2020) note that user-generated content and influencer collaborations increase BL interaction. The two points of view establish that relationship not only improves consumer relations but also the experience of building BL through active interaction providing value.

2.4 SM practices for improving brand loyalty in fashion

Loyalty to the specific brand is one of the most significant indicators in the fashion business, and the efficient use of SM plays a critical role in achieving this. As pointed out by Zhao et al. (2022), more engagement with the brands and loyalty from customers can be achieved through strategic collaborations with influencers and the use of better-quality visuals. On the other hand, Noris et al. (2021) emphasize the necessity of engaging practices like live chats and user-generated content campaigns that help to build a community and create a focus on personal interactions. Both approaches note that while having quality content is critical in reaching customers and maintaining strong BL in the fashion market, equal importance must be given to engagement tactics.

2.5 Theoretical framework

Some of the theories that can help explain SMM and BL include Social Exchange Theory and Customer Relationship Management (CRM). In the Social Exchange Theory, consumer relationships are based on the exchange of value; brands provide value through entertaining and engaging content or replies and requests for loyalty (Xuecheng, Iqbal & Saina, 2022). CRM centres on customer contacts to increase their loyalty through effective communication and

tailored marketing (Sommella & Sorrentino, 2023). In both theories, there is evidence of how specific SM activities can build the perceived value that is important for the emotional bond hence BL.

2.6 Conceptual framework

Figure 2.1: Conceptual framework

(Source: Self-created)

2.7 Literature gap

Although the current literature review shows that the general effects of SM have been widely studied in relation to consumer behaviour, the effect of SM on BL, particularly in the fashion business, has received relatively little attention. Most studies are generic, giving general approaches to using SM for business purposes without regard for how each kind of platform, or content posted influences BL. This gap highlights the need to conduct research that investigates platform characteristics and content impact on long-term consumers' engagement in fashion industry.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The research has taken an interpretivism approach which embraces the subjectivity of SM interactions and the experience of the consumers (Alharahsheh & Pius, 2020). It has adopted the inductive research strategy that implies observing particular phenomena or events to derive general patterns and conclusions. The exploratory design has been applied to analyze the mediating roles of SMM.

3.2 Data Collection Methods

This paper employed the secondary qualitative method of research. This led to gathering of different forms of information in the shortest time (Chatfield, 2020). To increase the credibility of this study, information was obtained from Google Scholar and other reliable Websites to obtain relevant information.

3.3 Data Analysis Technique

The research has used thematic analysis. This approach was to develop characteristics which on their own are peculiar to social media marketing and brand affinity. As a method, thematic analysis enabled achieving a systematic better understanding of how various strategies of the SM can influence consumer loyalty (Chatfield, 2020).

3.4 Ethical Considerations

The research has adhered to the necessary ethical concerns in the conduct of the research by insisting on the anonymized data (Pietilä et al. 2020). Since the work has involved only secondary sources, the emphasis has been laid down on such sources which are credible and authorized. Concerning the use of the same sources, it is important that the rights of owners of the copyrights still reign. In addition, the study has explained the limitations of the sources and has quoted them appropriately, to reduce instances of plagiarism and cheating in the entire research exercise.

Chapter 4: Findings and Discussion

4.1 Findings

Themes	Keywords	Sub-Themes
SM strategies significantly influence brand loyalty among UK consumers	Influence, Strategies, Loyalty	Platform effectiveness, Content impact
High consumer engagement on SM boosts brand loyalty in the UK	Engagement, Boost, Loyalty	Interaction quality, User involvement
Optimized SM practices can improve fashion brand loyalty in the UK	Optimization, Practices, Improvement	Best practices, Strategy recommendations

Table 4.1: Thematic coding

Theme 1: SM strategies significantly influence brand loyalty among UK consumers

Marketing communication through SM plays a vital role in influencing the consumers in the UK as they decide the buying behaviours and perception of the brands (Fetais et al. 2023). Some of the UK fashion brands, including ASOS as well as PrettyLittleThing have proved to a good examples of fashion brands that successfully employ SM to enhance consumer relationships as well as loyalty. For instance, as noted in the operational plan, ASOS has done well on influencer marketing where the influencers continually advertise the company’s products on Instagram and TikTok. Such has resulted in the buyers’ increasing confidence in the products and therefore purchasing the products at higher rates (Salem & Salem, 2021).

Figure 4.1: “Purchase odds after repeated influencer recommendation”

(Source: Statista Research Department, 2023)

In a survey conducted among UK citizens in the year 2022, it was established that influencer marketing has a positive impact on the impact made on the buying decisions (Statista Research Department, 2023). This was further confirmed as over two-thirds of fashion and lifestyle customers stated that they are more likely to buy a product endorsed by an influencer if the endorsement is consistent. Moreover, 44.44% of those polled said they are somewhat likely to buy, and 23.81% are much more likely to purchase being influenced by multiple influencers (Statista Research Department, 2023). The above data signifies an SM campaign’s ability to maintain incremental campaigns with branding affecting the consumer’s commitment to fashion brands.

Theme 2: High consumer engagement on SM boosts brand loyalty in the UK

There is a positive relationship between consumer engagement in the fashion industry and the adoption of BL in the United Kingdom. Brands which communicate well with their targeted public develop better relationships to have higher loyalty (Cuesta-Valiño, Gutiérrez-Rodríguez & Núñez-Barriopedro, 2022). For instance, Boohoo, which is a fashion retail company, has incorporated SM in a very innovative manner, offering an interactive live question and answer session, offering polls and users’ contributions. This approach improves the efforts of customer relations and makes them believe in the ability of the business to deliver the required services at the next time they require them.

Figure 4.2: “Probability for purchases on SM among UK fashion & lifestyle shoppers”

(Source: Statista Research Department, 2023)

This link is illustrated in a 2022 survey where most fashion and lifestyle consumers are willing to finish purchases using SM in case, they have trusted the brand or account (Statista Research Department, 2023). This shows that whenever consumers engage themselves thoroughly in communications and receive customized messages, there is a possibility that they will be triggered to make purchases. Still, more than 14% of respondents have already made direct purchases by following the links and engaging in SM advertising campaigns (Statista Research Department, 2023). However, per the survey, more than a fifth of consumers refuse to purchase through these social sites, meaning that brands should work round the clock to earn the trust and relevance of these potential clients.

Theme 3: Optimized SM practices can improve fashion brand loyalty in the UK

Best UK fashion practices involving SMM contribute to increasing BL. Such approaches are partnering with influencer marketing, coming up with quality content, and developing stimulating consumer engagement (Fetais et al. 2023). For instance, Zara a UK fashion brand has performed well keeping a continuous brand image across SM tools. In the case of Zara, the utilization of high-quality and attractive media content and speed in responding to fashion trends has cemented the consumers’ loyalty towards Zara’s brand.

Likewise, fashion retailer H&M has also followed SM strategies effectively to employ interactive stories and poll features on Instagram (Jiang, 2020). This approach serves to increase brand awareness and make the clients feel that they are actively participating in some activity. It is also worthwhile to note that H&M works with new influencers and fashion icons very often which makes the brand popular. Such practices are backed by evidence revealing that proper SM optimization translates to, enhanced customer retention. The brands that create relevant content and engaging activities have a better bond with the consumer and thus, there is higher customer loyalty and therefore higher customer retention in the fashion market.

4.2 Discussion

The study shows that SM, high consumer involvement, and practice improvements are critical factors that contribute to BL in the fashion industry within the UK. These findings are consistent with previous studies and shed light on the impact that proper management of SM can have on customers' behaviours and their attitudes towards the particular brand. One of them is that the use of SM strategies increases BL, as evidenced by the success of such brands as ASOS and PrettyLittleThing. ASOS's use of influencer marketing relates with similar studies pointing to the significance of consistent influencer promotion effect in enhancing consumer confidence and probability of purchase (Statista Research Department, 2023). This is evidenced in the literature with findings indicating that constant familiarization with the recommendations made by influencers results in better sales and increased brand affinity (Djafarova & Bowes, 2021)). This finding underlines the need to create strategic SM campaigns to improve customer perceptions and hence customer loyalty.

Another factor that contributes to the level of BL is high consumer interactivity on SM. Interaction with the customer through such features as clicking on a picture expresses the results of some studies that showed that engagement leads to loyalty, as in the case of Boohoo. The willingness of nearly half the respondents in the survey conducted in the UK in 2022 to check out through SM platforms with trust underlines the methods of engagement. This fact proves the significance of the optimised activity on SM platforms, which has been observed with such companies as Zara and H&M (Jiang, 2020). This corresponds to literature that calls for a different, visually appealing and engaging approach to SM that is specific to the brand to build loyalty among customers (Djafarova & Bowes, 2021). Strategies which have been employed by both brands to enhance loyalty have worked out well and comprise a social sense of community in line with the literature that highlights personalized and engaging SM practice as a sure way of creating and enhancing BL. The research objectives have been served well in showing how SM strategies impact BL, in evaluating consumer engagement and in proffering best practices. The results effectively support the understanding of how specific SM strategies promote the increase in customer BL in the UK fashion sector by complementing the prior findings and indicating directions for future study.

Chapter 5: Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

This present study shows that strategic SMM practices, high consumer interactions, and efficient approaches positively impact BL in the UK fashion industry. Some of these findings indicate that continuous influencer marketing and engaging consumer behaviour modification techniques that influence customers' perception significantly trigger BL. These findings are most relevant to the research questions that proposed a direct relationship between SM strategies and BL, the role of consumers in this process, and the efficiency of optimized strategies. It is critical to emphasise the research findings; the study provides worthwhile findings to those interested in understanding the implementation of SM platforms in the fashion industry. It offers specific suggestions for fashion companies that want to enhance customers' bonds and loyalty via SM. Thus, the research provides relevant insight into the existing literature concerning SMM and BL and provides specific suggestions for fashion brands to enhance the strength of consumer bonds. With the help of proper strategy in SM and focus on creating a high level of engagement brands will be able to improve the loyalty measures and achieve long-term success in the aggressively growing market. Thus, the study contributes to the knowledge collected in the course of the fashion industry's interaction with SM and opens up new opportunities for developing and improving these strategies even further.

5.2 Recommendations

Recommendation 1: Leverage Influencer Partnerships

Brands must carry on partnering with influencers for frequent promotion. Such recommendations can improve the level of consumers' confidence and increase the likelihood of a purchase (Jacobson & Harrison, 2022).

Recommendation 2: Increase Interactive Engagement

Encourage user participation by incorporating opportunities for polls, live question-and-answer sections, and material contributed by the consumer (Islam, 2022). This also strengthens the bond as well as customers' loyalty towards a particular brand.

Recommendation 3: Personalize Content

To optimise and aesthetically present individually relevant content to the audiences within target segments. The implementation of customized content can enhance the level of consumer engagement and thus improve the popularity of the brand (Chandra et al. 2022).

5.3 Limitations of the Study

The study has its limitations where the authors have relied on secondary data only, which may not represent the existing trends or consumer behaviour analysis appropriately. In the same regard, the study is conducted only on the UK fashion industry; therefore, it lacks generalizability to other regions or other industries.

5.4 Suggestions for Future Research

Future research could investigate how new SM platforms influence fashion BL to capture dynamic trends. Studying consumers' behaviour in other geographical areas or using different industries may improve the external validity of the study. Further, still, an attempt at primary data acquisition through surveys or interviews may give a more elaborate understanding of consumers' attitudes towards the product.

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